

ROMAN 4 - REGULAR DOMINATION NUMBER USING AN ALGORITHM OF A 4 – REGULAR GRAPH

DR.A.SUDHAKARAI AH*
PROFESSOR
DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS
SVU COLLEGE OF SCIENCES
S.V.UNIVERSITY
TIRUPATHI

C. GOUSIA SULTHANA CHOUDRI¹
LECTURER IN MATHEMATICS
RESEARCH SCHOLAR
KSN GOVT DEGREE COLLEGE FOR
WOMEN (A), ANANTAPUR.

DR. G V RAMESH BABU²
ASSOCIATE PROFESSOR
DEPT OF COMPUTER SCIENCE
S V UNIVERSITY ,TIRUPATI

1.1. ABSTRACT:

A Roman dominating function on a graph $G = (V, E)$ is a function $f : V \rightarrow \{0, 1, 2\}$ satisfying the condition that every vertex u for which $f(u) = 0$ is adjacent to at least one vertex v for which $f(v) = 2$. The weight of a Roman dominating function is the value $f(V) = \sum_{u \in V} f(u)$. The minimum weight of a Roman dominating function on a graph G is called the Roman domination number of G . A regular graph is a graph in which every vertex has the same degree. More specifically, a r -regular graph is a graph in which every vertex has degree r . Today graph theory is one of the most flourishing branches of modern mathematics. In this paper we will give the relationship between the Roman 4 – regular domination with 4 – Regular domination. This paper also gives the 4 – Regular dominating sets corresponding to the 4 – Regular graphs.

INDEXED TERMS :

Interval graph, Dominating set, 4 – Regular dominating set, Roman 4 – regular dominating set, 4 - regular domination number, Roman 4 – regular domination number.

1.2. PRELIMINARIES:

Domination is an area in graph theory with an extensive research activity. In 1998, a book [1] on domination has been published which lists 1222 papers in this area. In general, a dominating set in a graph is a set of vertices D such that each vertex is either in D or is adjacent to a vertex in D . A function $f : V \rightarrow \{0, 1, 2\}$ having the property that for every vertex $v \in V$ with $f(v) = 0$, there exists a vertex $u \in N(v)$ with $f(u) = 2$, is called a Roman dominating function or just an RDF. The weight of an RDF f is the sum $f(V) = \sum_{u \in V} f(u)$. The minimum weight of a RDF on G is called the Roman domination number of G . The mathematical concept of Roman domination, was developed by Cockayne

et al. [2]. Many variations, generalizations and applications of Roman domination parameters have been studied, and to see the latest progress until 2020 see [3–5].

Kammerling and Volkmann [6] introduced the concept of Roman k -domination in graphs. Let k be a positive integer. A Roman k -dominating function on G is a function $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1, 2\}$ such that every vertex u for which $f(u) = 0$ is adjacent to at least k vertices u_1, u_2, \dots, u_k with $f(u_i) = 2$, for $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$. The weight of a Roman k -dominating function is the value $w(f) = \sum_{u \in V} f(u)$. The minimum weight of a Roman k -dominating function on a graph G is called the Roman k -domination number $\gamma_{KR}(G)$ of G . The concept of Roman k -domination was further studied in [7].

In graph theory, a regular graph is a graph where each vertex has the same number of neighbors i.e. every vertex has the same degree. A regular graph with vertices of degree k is called a k -regular graph or regular graph of degree k . We consider finite and simple graphs G with vertex set $V = V(G)$ and edge set $E(G)$. The number of vertices of G is called the order of G . The degree of a vertex v , denoted by $\deg(v)$ or $\deg_G(v)$.

Let $I = \{I_1, I_2, I_3, I_4, \dots, I_n\}$ be any interval family, where each I_i is an interval on the real line and $I_i = [a_i, b_i]$, for $i = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, n$. Here a_i is called the left end point labeling and b_i is the right end point labeling of I_i . Without loss of generality, we assume that all the end points of the intervals in I are distinct numbers between 1 and $2n$. Two intervals i and j are said to be intersect each other if they have non - empty intersection.

A graph $G = (V, E)$ is an interval graph if the vertex set V can be put into one-to-one correspondence with a set of intervals I on the real line R such that two vertices of G are joined by an edge in E if and only if their corresponding intervals in I have non-empty intersection. That is if $i = [a_i, b_i]$ and $j = [a_j, b_j]$, then i and j intersect means either $a_j < b_i$ or $a_i < b_j$. The set I is called an interval representation of G and G is referred to as the intersection graph of I . Also we say that the intervals contain both its end points and that no two intervals share a common end point. The intervals and vertices of an interval graph are one and the same thing. The graph G is connected and the list of sorted end points is given and the intervals in I are indexed by increasing right end points that is $b_1 < b_2 < b_3 < \dots < b_n$.

$G(V, E)$ is a function $f: V \rightarrow \{0, 1, 2\}$ satisfying the condition that every vertex u for which $f(u) = 0$ is adjacent to at least one vertex v for which $f(v) = 2$. The weight of a Roman

dominating function is the value $f(v) = \sum_{v \in V} f(V)$. The minimum weight of a Roman dominating function on a graph G is called as the Roman domination number of G . It is denoted by $\gamma_R(G)$.

In graph theory a regular graph is a graph where each vertex has same number of neighbors i.e., every vertex has the same degree. If the degree of every vertex is equal to 4 then that graph is said to be a 4 – regular graph and the domination number is 4 – regular domination number and is denoted by $\gamma_{4R}(G)$. The Roman domination number of the 4 – regular graph is nothing but the Roman 4 – Regular domination number and is denoted by $\gamma_{R4R}(G)$.

1.3. EXPLANATION OF THE ALGORITHM

For finding the 4 – regular dominating set through an algorithm, we consider a connected interval graph. Let $G = (V, E)$ be a connected interval graph. According to the increasing order we set the intervals. First of all we treat none of a vertex of $V(G)$ is a member of 4 – regular dominating set 4 - RDS. Then insert vertices one by one by testing their consistency. If a vertex v is dominated by at least two vertices, then leave it, otherwise take the first highest numbered adjacent vertex from $N[v]$ as a member of 4 – RDS, if it is not adjacent to the next member of $N[v]$ or v is not the last vertex, clearly given in the algorithm of section 1.4.

Let us associate a new term $M_i(v)$, for a vertex $v \in V$, for all $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k (k = |N(v)|)$ to each adjacent vertices of v in order to IG ordering of intervals in the following way:

$$M_i(v) = \max \left\{ N[v] - \bigcup_{j=0}^{i-1} M_j(v) \right\}, \text{ with } M_0(v) = \max \{ N(v) \}$$

In connection with the highest numbered adjacent vertex of v , we call this $M_i(v)$ as the p - th numbered adjacent vertex of v . Let $u, v \in V$, if for some $i (i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, |N(v)|)$, $|N(v)| - i = p$ such that $u = M_i(v)$, then u is called the p - th numbered adjacent vertex of v .

1.4. ALGORITHM FOR K – REGULAR DOMINATING SET OF A K - REGULAR GRAPH

Input: A k - Regular graph $G = (V, E)$ with IG ordering vertex set $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$.

Output: k - Regular Dominating Set k - RDS.

Step 1: Set $f(j) = 0, \forall j = 1, 2, \dots, n$;

Step 2: Set $i = 1, K - RDS = \phi$;

Step 2.1: Compute $W_i(f) = \sum_{v \in N[i]} f(v)$;

Step 2.2: If $W_i(f) = 0$, then

Set $f(M_0(i)) = 1$ and $f(M_1(i)) = 1$;

take $K - RDS = \{M_0(i)\}$;

Step 2.3: else if $W_i(f) = 1$,

Step 2.3.1: if $f(M_i(i)) = 1$ and that $M_i(i)$ does not belongs 4 - RDS then take $M_i(i)$
into 4 - RDS

end if;

Step 2.3.2: if $f(M_i(i)) = 1$ and that $M_i(i)$ belongs 4 - RDS then take $M_{i+1}(i)$ or

$M_{i-1}(i)$ into 4 - RDS

end if;

Step 2.3.3: if $f(M_i(i)) = 1$ and that $M_i(i) = v_i$ belongs 4 - RDS and v_{i+1} or v_{i-1} or

both are the neighborhoods of that vertex then no change in 4 - RDS

end if;

Step 2.3.4: if $f(M_i(i)) = 1$ and that $M_i(i) = v_i$ belongs 4 - RDS and v_{i+1} or v_{i-1} or

both are not the neighborhoods of that vertex then we have to take M_{i-1} or M_{i+1} into
4 - RDS and set $f(M_{i-1})$ or $f(M_{i+1})$ equal to 1

end if;

Step 2.4: else if $W_i(f) \geq 2$, then

4 – RDS remains unchanged;

end if;

Step 2.5: Calculate $i = i + 1$ and go to Step 2.1 and continue until the last

vertex;

end 4 - RDS.

1.5. MAIN THEOREMS:

1.5.1. Theorem:

Let $I = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n\}$ be a n 4 – Regular interval family and G is a 4 - Regular graph corresponding to I . If v_i and v_{i+1} are any two intervals in I such that $v_{i+1} \in 4$ - RDS, where 4 - RDS is a 4 - Regular dominating set, v_{i+1} is not the last vertex. V_i intersects V_{i+2} which was the last vertex, then 4 - Regular domination occurs in G and the 4 – Regular domination number satisfies $\gamma_{R4R}(G) = 2^{\gamma_{4R}(G)}$, where $\gamma_{R4R}(G)$ is the Roman 4 – Regular domination number of the graph G .

Proof:

Let $I = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n\}$ be a n 4 – Regular interval family and G is a 4 - Regular graph corresponding to I . If v_i and v_{i+1} are any two intervals in I such that $v_{i+1} \in 4$ - RDS, where 4 – RDS is a 4 - Regular dominating set. V_i does not intersects the vertex V_{i+2} , then in the last iteration weight of the functions does not gives the value 2 or more as it was the last iteration and also not satisfies the algorithm. $|V_1| + 2|V_2|$ gives the Roman 4 – Regular domination number as it leads to the equality of $\gamma_{R4R}(G) = 2^{\gamma_{4R}(G)}$.

In this procedure we also find the 4 - Regular dominating set of a 4 - Regular graph towards the algorithm as given in section 1.4 with an illustration.

1.5.2. Illustration:

The 4 – Regular Graph G is as follows,

Fig. 2: 4 – Regular Graph G

4 – Regular dominating set 4 - RDS = $\{v_4, v_5\}$

From the above 4 – Regular graph G , the neighborhoods of each vertex are as follows,

nbd $[v_1] = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5\}$		nbd $[v_2] = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_6\}$				
nbd $[v_3] = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_5, v_6\}$		nbd $[v_4] = \{v_1, v_2, v_4, v_5, v_6\}$				
nbd $[v_5] = \{v_1, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6\}$		nbd $[v_6] = \{v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6\}$				
$M_i(v) \setminus v$	v_1	v_2	v_3	v_4	v_5	v_6
$M_0(v)$	v_5	v_6	v_6	v_6	v_6	v_6
$M_1(v)$	v_4	v_4	v_5	v_5	v_5	v_5
$M_2(v)$	v_3	v_3	v_3	v_4	v_4	v_4
$M_3(v)$	v_2	v_2	v_2	v_2	v_3	v_3
$M_4(v)$	v_1	v_1	v_1	v_1	v_1	v_2

To find the 4 – Regular dominating set, we have to compute all the p - th numbered adjacent vertices as above.

First set $f(j) = 0, \forall j \in V$. In step 2, set $i = 1, 4 - RDS = \phi$, that is initially 4 - RDS is empty. Step 2 repeats for n times. Here $n = 6$, the number of vertices in the 4 – Regular graph G . We follow the iterations of the illustration through the table.

Iteration (1)

For the first iteration $i = 1$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_1] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5 \}$$

$$w_1(f) = f(\text{N}[v_1])$$

$$\begin{aligned} w_1(f) &= f(v_1) + f(v_2) + f(v_3) + f(v_4) + f(v_5) \\ &= 0 + 0 + 0 + 0 + 0 = 0 \end{aligned}$$

The first condition of if-end if is satisfied. Since $w_1(f) = 0$, we find $M_0(v_1) = v_5$ and $M_1(v_1) = v_4$. Then set

$$f(v_4) = 1 \text{ and } f(v_5) = 1$$

$$\text{Also set } 4\text{-RDS} = \phi \cup \{v_5\} \Rightarrow 4\text{-RDS} = \{v_5\}$$

Iteration (2)

For the second iteration $i = 2$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_2] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_6 \}$$

$$w_2(f) = f(\text{N}[v_2])$$

$$\begin{aligned} w_2(f) &= f(v_1) + f(v_2) + f(v_3) + f(v_4) + f(v_6) \\ &= 0 + 0 + 0 + 1 + 0 = 1 \end{aligned}$$

$f(v_4) = 1$ and $M_1(v_2) = v_4$ and does not belongs to 4-RDS then

$$4\text{-RDS} = \{v_4, v_5\}$$

The iteration number i is being increased to 3.

Iteration (3)

For the third iteration $i = 3$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_3] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3, v_5, v_6 \}$$

$$w_3(f) = f(N[v_3])$$

$$\begin{aligned} w_3(f) &= f(v_1)+f(v_2)+ f(v_3)+ f(v_5)+f(v_6) \\ &= 0+0+0+1+0 = 1 \end{aligned}$$

In this iteration $f(v_5)=1$ and v_6 was neighborhood of $i=3$ then no change in the 4 - RDS.

The iteration number i is being increased to 4.

Iteration (4)

For the fourth iteration $i = 4$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_4] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_4, v_5, v_6 \}$$

$$w_4(f) = f(N[v_4])$$

$$\begin{aligned} w_4(f) &= f(v_1)+ f(v_2)+ f(v_4)+ f(v_5)+f(v_6) \\ &= 0+0+1+1+0 = 2 \end{aligned}$$

In this iteration 4 - RDS remains unchanged. The iteration number i is being increased to 5.

Iteration (5)

For the fifth iteration $i = 5$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_5] = \{ v_1, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6 \}$$

$$w_5(f) = f(N[v_5])$$

$$\begin{aligned} w_5(f) &= f(v_1)+ f(v_3)+ f(v_4)+f(v_5) +f(v_6) \\ &= 0+0+1+1+0 = 2 \end{aligned}$$

In this iteration 4 - RDS remains unchanged.

The iteration number i is being increased to 6.

Iteration (6)

For the fifth iteration $i=6$

$$\text{Nbd}[v_6] = \{v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6\}$$

$$W_6(f) = f(N[v_6])$$

$$\begin{aligned} W_6(f) &= f(v_2) + f(v_3) + f(v_4) + f(v_5) + f(v_6) \\ &= 0 + 0 + 1 + 1 + 0 = 2 \end{aligned}$$

In this iteration 4 - RDS remains unchanged.

Now stop the iteration process as v_6 was the last vertex.

The cardinality of 4 - RDS = 2 and the Roman 4 - Regular domination number is given as 4. As 4 - RDS = $\{v_4, v_5\}$

$$\begin{aligned} |V_1| &= \{\emptyset\}, V_2 = \{v_4, v_5\} \\ \sum_{v \in V} f(v) &= |V_1| + 2|V_2| \\ &= 0 + 2 \cdot 2 = 4 \end{aligned}$$

Satisfies $\gamma_{R4R}(G) = 2^{\gamma_{4R}(G)}$ Hence the theorem is proved.

1.5.3. Theorem:

Let G be a 4 - Regular interval graph corresponding to an interval family $I = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n\}$. If v_i and v_j are any two intervals in I such that v_j belongs to 4 - RDS and it was the last vertex in the interval family, then 4 - Regular domination occurs in G and the 4 - Regular domination number $\gamma_{4R}(G)$ satisfies the property $\gamma_{R4R}(G) = 2^{\gamma_{4R}(G)}$, where $\gamma_{R4R}(G)$ is the Roman 4 - Regular domination number of the graph G .

Proof:

Let G be a 4 - Regular interval graph corresponding to an interval family $I = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n\}$. If v_i and v_j are any two intervals in I such that v_j belongs to 4 - RDS and which was the last vertex in the interval family. As it was the last vertex and also belongs to the 4 - Regular dominating set 4 - RDS, it definitely intersects the first vertex, otherwise it leads to contradiction for the 4 - Regular domination property, as it was the 4 - Regular interval graph

so that every vertex has the degree 4. We will find the 4 – Regular dominating set as follows from a 4 - Regular graph using the algorithm as explained in section 1.4.

1.5.4. Illustration:

The 4 - Regular graph G is as follows,

Fig.5: 4 - Regular graph G

The neighborhoods of each vertex from the above 4 - Regular graph G are as follows,

$nb\delta [v_1] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3, v_6, v_7 \}$	$nb\delta [v_2] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_7 \}$
$nb\delta [v_3] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5 \}$	$nb\delta [v_4] = \{ v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6 \}$
$nb\delta [v_5] = \{ v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6, v_7 \}$	$nb\delta [v_6] = \{ v_1, v_4, v_5, v_6, v_7 \}$
$nb\delta [v_7] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_5, v_6, v_7 \}$	

To find the 4 – Regular dominating set, we have to compute all the p - th numbered adjacent vertices as below,

$M_i(v) \setminus v$	v_1	v_2	v_3	v_4	v_5	v_6	v_7
$M_0(v)$	v_7	v_7	v_5	v_6	v_7	v_7	v_7
$M_1(v)$	v_6	v_4	v_4	v_5	v_6	v_6	v_6

$M_2(v)$	v_3	v_3	v_3	v_4	v_5	v_5	v_5
$M_3(v)$	v_2	v_2	v_2	v_3	v_4	v_4	v_2
$M_4(v)$	v_1	v_1	v_1	v_2	v_3	v_1	v_1

First set $f(j) = 0, \forall j \in V$. In step 2, set $i=1$, 4 - RDS = ϕ , that is initially 4 - RDS is empty. Step 2 repeats for n times. Here $n=7$ the number of vertices in the 4 - Regular graph G . As follows the iterations through the table,

Iteration (1)

For the first iteration $i = 1$

$$\text{Nbd}[v_1] = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_6, v_7\}$$

$$w_1(f) = f(\text{N}[v_1])$$

$$w_1(f) = f(v_1) + f(v_2) + f(v_3) + f(v_6) + f(v_7)$$

$$= 0 + 0 + 0 + 0 + 0 = 0$$

The first condition of if-end if is satisfied. Since $w_1(f) = 0$, we find $M_0(v_1) = v_7$ and $M_1(v_1) = v_6$. Then set

$$f(v_6) = 1 \text{ and } f(v_7) = 1$$

$$\text{Also set } 4\text{-RDS} = \phi \cup \{v_7\} \Rightarrow 4\text{-RDS} = \{v_7\}$$

Iteration (2)

For the second iteration $i = 2$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_2] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_7 \}$$

$$w_2(f) = f(N[v_2])$$

$$w_2(f) = f(v_1)+f(v_2)+ f(v_3)+ f(v_4)+ f(v_7)$$

$$= 0+0+0+0+1 = 1$$

So, in this iteration $M_0(v_2)=v_7$

Here if end if condition was satisfied. Since v_{7+1} not exists and v_{7-1} ie., v_6 was not the neighborhood of v_2 , hence take v_4 into 4 – RDS and also set $f(v_4)=1$

Which implies 4 – RDS = $\{ v_4, v_7 \}$, i is being increased to 3.

Iteration (3):

For the third iteration $i = 3$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_3] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5 \}$$

$$w_3(f) = f(N[v_3])$$

$$w_3(f) = f(v_1)+f(v_2)+ f(v_3)+ f(v_4)+f(v_5)$$

$$= 0+0+0+1+0 = 1$$

Here v_4 belongs to 4 – RDS and v_{4+1} was the neighborhood of v_3 , then no change to the 4 – RDS. In this iteration 4 – RDS remains unchanged. The iteration number i is being increased to 4.

Iteration (4):

For the fourth iteration $i = 4$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_4] = \{ v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6 \}$$

$$w_4(f) = f(N[v_4])$$

$$w_4(f) = f(v_2)+ f(v_3)+ f(v_4)+f(v_5)+f(v_6)$$

$$= 0+0+1+0+1 = 2$$

In this iteration also 4 – RDS remains unchanged. The iteration number i is being increased to 5.

Iteration (5):

For the fifth iteration $i = 5$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_5] = \{ v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6, v_7 \}$$

$$w_5(f) = f(N[v_5])$$

$$w_5(f) = f(v_3) + f(v_4) + f(v_5) + f(v_6) + f(v_7)$$

$$= 0+1+0+1+1 = 3$$

We go to step 2.4 and $W_5(f) \geq 2$, No change in 4 – RDS

Now we go to the next iteration

Iteration (6):

For the sixth iteration $i = 6$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_6] = \{ v_1, v_4, v_5, v_6, v_7 \}$$

$$w_6(f) = f(N[v_6])$$

$$w_6(f) = f(v_1) + f(v_4) + f(v_5) + f(v_6) + f(v_7)$$

$$= 0+1+0+1+1 = 3$$

We go to step 2.4 and $W_6(f) \geq 2$, No change in 4 – RDS

Now we go to the next iteration

Iteration (7):

For the sixth iteration $i=7$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_7] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_5, v_6, v_7 \}$$

$$W_7(f) = f(N[v_7])$$

$$\begin{aligned} W_7(f) &= f(v_1)+f(v_2)+f(v_5) +f(v_6) +f(v_7) \\ &= 0+0+0+1+1 = 2 \end{aligned}$$

We go to step 2.4 and $W_7(f) \geq 2$, No change in 4 – RDS

As v_7 was last vertex, it stops the iteration process here.

The cardinality of 4 - RDS = 2 and the Roman 4 – Regular domination number is given as 4. As 4 - RDS = $\{v_4, v_7\}$

$$\begin{aligned} |V_1| &= \{\emptyset\}, V_2 = \{v_4, v_7\} \\ \sum_{v \in V} f(v) &= |V_1| + 2|V_2| \\ &= 0 + 2 \cdot 2 = 4 \end{aligned}$$

satisfies $\gamma_{R4R}(G) = 2^{\gamma_{4R}(G)}$ Hence the theorem is proved.

1.5.5. Theorem:

Let us consider an n interval family $I = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n\}$ and G be a 4 -Regular graph of I . If v_1, v_2, v_3 are any three intervals in the interval family, v_1 intersects v_2 and v_2 intersects v_3 and v_1 does not intersects v_3 , then 4 – Regular domination occurs in G with $\gamma_{R4R}(G) = 2^{\gamma_{4R}(G)}$, where $\gamma_{R4R}(G)$ is the Roman 4 – Regular domination number of the graph G and $\gamma_{4R}(G)$ is the 4 – Regular domination number of the graph G .

Proof:

Let us consider an n interval family $I = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n\}$ and G be a 4 -Regular graph of I . If v_1, v_2, v_3 are any three intervals in the interval family, v_1 intersects v_2 and v_2 intersects v_3 and v_1 does not intersects v_3 . Also v_3 intersects v_4 and v_4 intersects v_5 but v_5 does not intersects v_3 , as it was the cycle each and every vertex satisfies the same property. 4 – Regular graph gives the degree 4 for every vertex, then every vertex must intersects atleast one of the vertex which belongs to 4 – RDS. Then Clearly 4 – Regular domination occurs in G and the cardinality gives $\gamma_{R4R}(G) = 2^{\gamma_{4R}(G)}$, where $\gamma_{R4R}(G)$ is the Roman 4 – Regular domination number of the graph G and $\gamma_{4R}(G)$ is the 4 – Regular domination number of the graph G .

$|V_1| = \{\emptyset\}, |V_2| = 2, \sum_{v \in V} f(v) = |V_1| + 2|V_2|$, satisfies $\gamma_{R4R}(G) = 2^{\gamma_{4R}(G)}$. Now we will find the 4

- Regular dominating set using the algorithm as given in section 1.4 as follows,

1.5.6. Illustration:

The 4 – Regular graph G is as follows,

Fig.8: 4 – Regular graph G

The corresponding neighborhoods of each vertex of the above 4 – Regular graph G are as follows,

$nb\delta [v_1] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_4, v_6, v_8 \}$	$nb\delta [v_2] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3, v_5, v_7 \}$
$nb\delta [v_3] = \{ v_2, v_3, v_4, v_6, v_8 \}$	$nb\delta [v_4] = \{ v_1, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_7 \}$
$nb\delta [v_5] = \{ v_2, v_4, v_5, v_6, v_8 \}$	$nb\delta [v_6] = \{ v_1, v_3, v_5, v_6, v_7 \}$
$nb\delta [v_7] = \{ v_2, v_4, v_6, v_7, v_8 \}$	$nb\delta [v_8] = \{ v_1, v_3, v_5, v_7, v_8 \}$

To find the 4 – Regular dominating set, we have to compute all the p - th numbered adjacent vertices as follows,

$M_i(v) \setminus v$	v_1	v_2	v_3	v_4	v_5	v_6	v_7	v_8
$M_0(v)$	v_8	v_7	v_8	v_7	v_8	v_7	v_8	v_8
$M_1(v)$	v_6	v_5	v_6	v_5	v_6	v_6	v_7	v_7
$M_2(v)$	v_4	v_3	v_4	v_4	v_5	v_5	v_6	v_5
$M_3(v)$	v_2	v_2	v_3	v_3	v_4	v_3	v_4	v_3
$M_4(v)$	v_1	v_1	v_2	v_1	v_2	v_1	v_2	v_1

First set $f(j) = 0, \forall j \in V$. Set 4 - RDS = ϕ , that is initially 4 - RDS is empty. Step 2 repeats for n times. Here $n = 8$, the number of vertices in the 4 - Regular graph G . As follows iterations,

Iteration (1)

For the first iteration $i = 1$

$$\text{Nbd}[v_1] = \{v_1, v_2, v_4, v_6, v_8\}$$

$$w_1(f) = f(\text{N}[v_1])$$

$$w_1(f) = f(v_1) + f(v_2) + f(v_4) + f(v_6) + f(v_8)$$

$$= 0 + 0 + 0 + 0 + 0 = 0$$

The first condition of if-end if is satisfied. Since $w_1(f) = 0$, we find $M_0(v_1) = v_8$ and $M_1(v_1) = v_6$. Then set

$$f(v_6) = 1 \text{ and } f(v_8) = 1$$

$$\text{Also set } 4\text{-RDS} = \phi \cup \{v_8\} \Rightarrow 4\text{-RDS} = \{v_8\}$$

Iteration (2)

For the second iteration $i = 2$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_2] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3, v_5, v_7 \}$$

$$w_2(f) = f(N[v_2])$$

$$w_2(f) = f(v_1)+f(v_2)+ f(v_3)+ f(v_5) + f(v_7)$$

$$= 0+0+0+0+0 = 0$$

The first condition of if-end if is satisfied. Since we find $w_2(f) = 0$ $M_0(v_2)$
 $= v_7$ and $M_1(v_2) = v_5$. Then set

$$f(v_5) = 1 \text{ and } f(v_7) = 1$$

Also set $4 - \text{RDS} = \{v_8\} \cup \{v_7\} \Rightarrow 4 - \text{RDS} = \{v_7, v_8\}$ and i is being increased to 3.

Iteration (3)

For the third iteration $i = 3$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_3] = \{ v_2, v_3, v_4, v_6, , v_8 \}$$

$$w_3(f) = f(N[v_3])$$

$$w_3(f) = f(v_2)+f(v_3)+ f(v_4)+ f(v_6)+f(v_8)$$

$$= 0+0+0+1+1 = 2$$

In this iteration 4 – RDS remains unchanged.

The iteration number i is being increased to 4.

Iteration (4)

For the fourth iteration $i = 4$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_4] = \{ v_1, v_3, v_4, v_5 , v_7 \}$$

$$w_4(f) = f(N[v_4])$$

$$w_4(f) = f(v_1)+f(v_3)+ f(v_4)+ f(v_5)+f(v_7)$$

$$= 0+0+0+1+1 = 2$$

In this iteration 4 – RDS remains unchanged.

The iteration number i is being increased to 5.

Iteration (5)

For the fifth iteration $i = 5$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_5] = \{v_2, v_4, v_5, v_6, v_8\}$$

$$w_5(f) = f(N[v_5])$$

$$w_5(f) = f(v_2) + f(v_4) + f(v_5) + f(v_6) + f(v_8)$$

$$= 0+0+1+1+1 = 3$$

In this iteration 4 – RDS remains unchanged, as by Step 2.4 in the Algorithm.

The iteration number i is being increased to 5.

Iteration (6)

For the sixth iteration $i = 6$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_6] = \{v_1, v_3, v_5, v_6, v_7\}$$

$$w_6(f) = f(N[v_6])$$

$$w_6(f) = f(v_1) + f(v_3) + f(v_5) + f(v_6) + f(v_7)$$

$$= 0+0+1+1+1 = 3$$

The iteration number i is being increased to 7.

Iteration (7)

For the seventh iteration $i = 7$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_7] = \{v_2, v_4, v_6, v_7, v_8\}$$

$$w_7(f) = f(N[v_7])$$

$$w_7(f) = f(v_2) + f(v_4) + f(v_6) + f(v_7) + f(v_8)$$

$$= 0+0+1+1+1 =3$$

The iteration number i is being increased to 8.

Iteration (8)

For the seventh iteration $i = 8$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_8] = \{ v_1, v_3, v_5, v_7, v_8 \}$$

$$W_8(f) = f(N[v_8])$$

$$W_8(f) = f(v_1) + f(v_3) + f(v_5) + f(v_7) + f(v_8)$$

$$= 0+0+1+1+1 =3$$

$$\text{Therefore 4 - RDS} = \{v_7, v_8\}$$

Thus it completes the iteration process and gives the final 4 - Regular dominating set. satisfies $\gamma_{R4R}(G) = 2^{\gamma_{4R}(G)}$. Hence the theorem is proved.

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